

ISic1507

I.Sicily inscription 1507

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra di Fuardo)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Found by Orsi in 1928 in excavation in contrada Diana, reused in cover
of t.22

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 2384

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θεοδώρου

Apparatus

Text of ML186

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645008

PHI 334288

Bibliography

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